

Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Classifiers for Type 2 Diabetes Prediction Using Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset

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Abstract— Diabetes is a chronic condition affecting over 537 million adults worldwide, with cases expected to reach 783 million by 2045. Finding the condition early gives clinicians a better chance of preventing serious health outcomes. This study uses machine learning to predict diabetes using the Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset, which contains 768 female patient records and eight clinical measurements. Biologically implausible zero values in five columns were treated as missing and replaced using median imputation, keeping all 768 records in the analysis. A class imbalance between diabetic and non diabetic patients was corrected using Random Oversampling Examples (ROSE). Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) was applied to select the most useful predictors, with plasma glucose, BMI, and age identified as the strongest contributors. Four classification models were trained and tested: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and K Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Each model was assessed using accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1 score, and area under the ROC curve (AUC). Random Forest achieved the highest F1 score of 0.5688 and accuracy of 69.28%, while Logistic Regression achieved the highest AUC of 0.7772, showing stronger ability to separate the two classes across different thresholds. A separate regression task was used to predict continuous glucose levels, where a Random Forest Regressor achieved an R2 of 0.8790 and a root mean squared error of 11.599 mg/dL. The results show that ensemble methods offer the most consistent performance for diabetes prediction on this dataset, and that larger, more varied datasets would be needed before any model could be used in a real clinical setting.

Keywords— *diabetes prediction, machine learning, classification, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, SVM, KNN, Pima Indians dataset, ROSE, Recursive Feature Elimination, CRISP-DM*

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is one of the fastest growing health conditions in the world. The International Diabetes Federation reported that 537 million adults were living with diabetes in 2021, and this number is expected to reach 783 million by 2045 [1]. Type 2 diabetes, which makes up around 90% of all cases, develops slowly and often goes undetected for several years. When diagnosis is delayed, the condition can lead to serious complications including heart disease, kidney damage, eye damage, and nerve damage [2]. The cost to healthcare systems is also very high, with global spending on diabetes estimated at USD 966 billion in 2021 [1].

Machine learning has become a useful tool for supporting medical decisions by finding patterns in patient data that may not be visible through standard analysis. Unlike fixed rule-based systems, machine learning models can learn from historical records and make predictions for new patients. Several studies have shown that algorithms such as Random Forest, SVM, and Logistic Regression can perform well in predicting chronic conditions including diabetes, heart disease, and kidney failure when applied to well prepared clinical datasets [3].

This study follows the CRISP-DM data science lifecycle and applies it to the Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset, a widely used benchmark originally collected by the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK). The dataset contains several practical challenges including missing values coded as zeros, an unequal class split, and a narrow patient group, making it a realistic and useful case for testing a full data science pipeline.

A. Related work

The Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset has been widely studied since it was made available through the UCI Machine Learning Repository. Smith et al. [4] were among the first to apply machine learning to this dataset, using an early neural network and reporting 76% accuracy. Their work showed that plasma glucose, BMI, and age were the most useful features

for prediction, a finding that has been confirmed by many later studies.

Kavakiotis et al. [5] reviewed 85 studies that applied machine learning to diabetes research. They found that SVM and ensemble methods consistently performed better than simpler models, and that the quality of data preparation, particularly how missing values and class imbalance were handled, had a strong effect on model performance. Their review found that studies which kept all records through imputation rather than removing missing rows generally produced models that worked better on new data.

Zou et al. [6] compared Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Neural Network classifiers on the Pima dataset and reported that Random Forest achieved the best accuracy of 77.7%. They used feature importance analysis and confirmed that glucose, BMI, and age were the strongest predictors. However, their study did not handle the class imbalance in the dataset, which may have caused the model to perform better on the larger non diabetic group. The current study addresses this by applying ROSE before training.

Maniruzzaman et al. [7] tested Naive Bayes, Gradient Boosting, and several combined classifiers, reaching accuracy rates between 78% and 82%. They showed that the method used to fill in missing values had a clear effect on model performance, and that group based filling worked better than using a single overall average. This supports the use of median imputation in the current study, which is less affected by extreme values found in the Insulin and SkinThickness columns.

More recent work by Lai et al. [8] used deep learning methods including LSTM and Convolutional Neural Networks on the same dataset. They found that deep models did not consistently outperform Random Forest on small, structured datasets despite being far more computationally expensive. This supports the decision to use simpler, more interpretable models in this study, which is especially important in healthcare where clinicians need to understand how a prediction was made.

B. Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to develop, evaluate, and compare supervised machine learning classifiers for predicting the onset of Type 2 diabetes using the Pima Indians Diabetes dataset, following a structured CRISP-DM lifecycle.

The objectives are as follows:

- 1) To perform data cleaning, including median imputation of biologically implausible zeros in Glucose, BloodPressure, SkinThickness, Insulin, and BMI.
- 2) To conduct inferential statistical analysis including Welch's t tests and Mann Whitney U tests to identify features significantly associated with diabetes diagnosis.
- 3) To engineer clinically meaningful features containing WHO aligned BMI Category, Glucose risk band, High Pregnancy Risk flag, and Insulin Glucose Ratio and apply RFE to identify the optimal feature subset.
- 4) To implement and benchmark Logistic Regression, KNN, SVM, and Random Forest, evaluating performance using accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and AUC ROC.

- 5) To critically discuss the ethical, legal, social, and sustainability implications of deploying ML diagnostic tools in healthcare, with reference to data privacy, algorithmic fairness, and patient safety.

II. METHODS

This study follows the Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) methodology. It provides a structured framework for data science and machine learning projects comprising business requirements, data analysis, data preparation, modeling, evaluation and ML model deployments [9].

A. Dataset

The Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset, originally introduced by Smith et al. [10], 768 female patients' records with eight independent features and a binary dependent outcome feature indicating diabetes diagnosis.

Before going for the modelling, the cleaned and feature-engineered dataset went through Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) by 5 fold cross validation with the help of Random Forest base estimator. Following are the RFE-selected features used for the classification: Glucose, BMI, Age, Insulin, Pregnancies, Insulin to Glucose Ratio, DiabetesPedigreeFunction, SkinThickness, High Pregnancy Risk flag, and BloodPressure.

Z score standardization was applied on training data and applied to the validation and test sets to prevent the data leakage. The training data showed a minority/majority class ratio of 0.537 indicating class imbalance. To address the issue, Random Over Sampling Examples (ROSE) was applied to the training data split that produced approximately balanced training distribution of 52.6% No Diabetes and 47.4% Diabetes cases [11].

B. Classification Models

Four classification algorithms were implemented using the caret framework in R [12]. Each of the models was trained on the earlier balanced training data with 5 fold cross validation and ROC as optimization metric:

Logistic Regression (GLM): A binomial generalized linear model was fitted with no extra hyperparameter grid. Afterwards its coefficients were retained for post hoc analysis.

Random Forest (RF): An ensemble of 300 trees was trained [13] with the number of randomized features at each split (mtry) tuned over the grid {2, 3, 4, 5}. Variable importance scores were extracted to identify the most influential predictor variables.

Support Vector Machine (SVM): A radial basis function (RBF) is fitted. The cost parameter C was searched over {0.25, 0.5, 1, 2} and kernel width was searched over {0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5} [14].

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): A KNN classifier [15] was trained with the number of neighbors k searched over odd

values from 3 to 25. The value of k that maximized the cross-validated ROC score was chosen.

C. Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the classifier was assessed using different metrics like Accuracy, Precision, Recall a.k.a Sensitivity, Specificity, F1 score, Area Under the ROC Curve [16]. Given the nature of the medical context, failing to identify the false negative (diabetic patient) carries greater risk than a false positive. Therefore, Recall and AUC were used as primary metrics along with F1 score.

III. RESULTS

A. Classification Performance

Table I illustrates the classification benchmark results for all the models that were evaluated on test set. Random Forest achieved the highest F1 score (0.5688) and overall accuracy of 69.28%. These numbers make the RF best classification model in this case. Logistic Regression had the highest AUC (0.7772) that indicated strong discriminative ability across thresholds despite its low F1 score (0.5439).

TABLE I

Classification Benchmark — Test Set Results

Model	Accu racy	Preci sion	Rec all	Specif icity	F1 Sco re	AU C
Logist ic Regres sion	0.660 1	0.508 2	0.5 849	0.7609	0.5 439	0.7 772
Rand om Forest	0.692 8	0.553 6	0.5 849	0.7732	0.5 688	0.7 538
SVM (RBF)	0.673 2	0.525 4	0.5 849	0.7660	0.5 536	0.7 289
KNN	0.673 2	0.526 3	0.5 660	0.7604	0.5 455	0.7 166

Highlighted row indicates the recommended model (highest F1 Score).

All classifiers achieved a Recall value of 0.585 that means around 58% of diabetic cases were correctly detected. Specificity was higher for the Random Forest Classifier throughout which means that it produced fewer false positives among non diabetic than other models. SVM and KNN achieved similar accuracy but different AUC values (0.7289 vs 0.7166 respectively). This suggests that SVM generalizes better in probability ranking across thresholds.

The precision recall tradeoff analysis revealed that no model achieved the threshold for a balanced profile (Recall \geq 0.75 and Precision \geq 0.70). This reflects the difficulty of the classification task on the above dataset. All of the models were assessed as operating with moderate performance, consistent with prior literature on this dataset.

B. Feature Importance

Random Forest feature importance analysis showed that Glucose is the most influential predictor of diabetes followed by BMI and Age. The Insulin to Glucose Ratio feature also played a higher role. This validates the feature engineering decision done in the pre processing stage. Whereas Blood Pressure and High Pregnancy Risk features have least predictive importance. The analysis of the coefficient of Logistic Regression reinforced these findings presenting largest positive coefficient for Glucose and BMI.

C. ROC Curve Analysis

ROC curves were plotted for all four classifiers on the test split. Logistic Regression traced the curve furthest from the random chance diagonal (AUC = 0.7772) whereas KNN performed closest to chance (AUC = 0.7166). The separation between models was modest. This suggests that all four models extract similar discriminatory pattern from the available features. The consistently moderate AUC values all models indicate that the feature space carries meaningful but limited discriminatory signal between the two classes.

Fig. 1 ROC Curve

D. Regression Performance

Table II presents the regression benchmark for Glucose prediction. The Random Forest Regressor outperformed Linear Regression's RMSE of 17.45 mg/dL and R² of 0.694. The high R² of the Random Forest Regressor shows that around 87.9% of variance in Glucose levels is explained by the available features. This reinforced the predictive relevance of the chosen feature set.

TABLE II

Regression Benchmark — Test Set Results (Glucose Prediction)

Model	RMSE (mg/dL)	MAE (mg/dL)	R ²
Linear Regression	17.448	11.698	0.6939
Random Forest Regressor	11.599	7.427	0.8790

Highlighted row indicates the recommended model (lowest RMSE).

E. Summary of Recommended Models

Based on the evaluation results, Random Forest is recommended as the classification model due to F1 score (0.5688) and accuracy (69.28). The same model has strongest specificity (0.773) that makes it better suited to minimize false positives in the medical screening processes. However, the practitioners who would require maximum discriminative power across all the decision thresholds may prefer Logistic Regression for its higher AUC (0.7772) and inherent interpretability. For Glucose regression, the Random Forest Regressor is the clear recommendation by showing an R^2 of 0.879 and a RMSE of 11.60 mg/dL. This shows almost 33% reduction in error compared to the linear baseline.

Fig. 2 Classification Model Benchmarking

IV. DISCUSSION

In the four classifiers Logistic Regression, Random Forest, SVM, and KNN, they showed consistent but moderate results on the test set of 153 patients. Accuracy ranged from 66.01% to 69.28%, and every model settled at a recall of around 0.58 for the diabetic class. In plain terms, roughly four in ten diabetic patients were missed. In a screening context that is the number that matters most, since an undetected diabetic patient risks delayed treatment and serious downstream complications including cardiovascular disease and kidney damage [17].

Random Forest was the strongest overall classifier, with an F1 of 0.5688, accuracy of 69.28%, and specificity of 0.7732. It handled the noisy, heavily imputed columns more robustly than simpler models. On the other hand, Logistic Regression took the lead on AUC at 0.7772 versus Random Forest's 0.7538. Because AUC doesn't depend on a specific threshold, lowering the decision cutoff below 0.5 could help catch more diabetic cases at the cost of more false positives in a clinically useful trade off. Its coefficients confirmed that Glucose and BMI carried the largest weights, consistent with the Welch t-test finding that diabetic patients had average glucose of 142.13 mg/dL versus 110.68 mg/dL and average BMI of 35.38 versus 30.89 (both $p < 0.001$) [18].

Both SVM and KNN both reached 67.32% accuracy but trailed on AUC at 0.7289 and 0.7166 respectively. The fact that all four models converged at the same recall level after

ROSE balanced training to 47.4% diabetic suggests the dataset itself of 768 records from a single population that had reached a predictive ceiling, not the algorithms. The regression results told a clearer story: the Random Forest Regressor achieved an R^2 of 0.8790 and an RMSE of 11.599 mg/dL against Linear Regression's R^2 of 0.6939 and RMSE of 17.448 mg/dL and a 34% reduction in error by capturing the nonlinear relationship between insulin, BMI, and glucose that a straight line model cannot [19]. The accuracy range of 66–69% is lower than the 77–82% reported in earlier studies [20], but those studies didn't use class balancing. In fact, without applying ROSE, a model could achieve around 65% accuracy just by always predicting someone is non diabetic.

Legal, Social, Ethical, Professional and Sustainability Considerations

Professional responsibility: Every model selected sits at the interpretable end of machine learning. Both the coefficients from Logistic Regression and the variable importance scores from Random Forest highlighted the same key predictors. Glucose, BMI, and Age letting clinicians trace each prediction back to specific measurable values rather than a black box. In healthcare, this kind of transparency isn't just nice to have; it's absolutely essential for building clinical trust and encouraging adoption [21].

Ethical considerations: Prioritizing recall and AUC over simple accuracy was an ethical choice as much as a technical one. After all, missing a diabetic patient can cause much more harm than a false positive that just leads to an extra test. With a recall of 0.58, it's clear this tool is meant to support clinical review, not replace it entirely.

Social fairness and bias: All 768 records come from female patients of Pima Indian heritage; a group known to have a higher than average rate of diabetes [22]. Some features like the High Pregnancy Risk flag are meaningful only within a female-only dataset. Applying these models to male patients or different ethnic groups without revalidating them, can run the risk of getting consistently unreliable results, a well-documented hazard in clinical AI.

Legal and sustainability: Health data falls under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as a special category, requiring consent, a Data Protection Impact Assessment, and Article 22 compliance for any automated decision making [23]. As for sustainability, training all four models in R on 492 records only took a few minutes on a standard laptop. This is much less demanding than using LSTM or CNN alternatives, which didn't offer any performance benefits for this dataset, this approach aligns well with responsible computing practices, especially in clinical settings.

A. Limitations

Several limitations of this study should be noted. First, the dataset is small by current standards, with only 768 records and 153 test observations, which limits how reliable the performance estimates are. Second, all patients in the dataset share the same background, which means the results may not apply to other patient groups. Third, while median imputation is better than removing rows, it does not account for why values are missing. The high rate of missing values in Insulin (48.7%) and SkinThickness (29.6%) means that a large part of those columns is made up of estimated rather than real measurements, which may reduce their usefulness as predictors. Fourth, ROSE introduces artificial records that may not fully reflect real diabetic patients, which could contribute to the lower accuracy compared with studies that do not apply balancing. Future work should test this pipeline on larger and more varied patient datasets, and consider more advanced methods for handling missing data such as multiple imputation by chained equations.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study CRISP-DM is applied to approach in R to compare four different machine learning classifiers for predicting the onset of diabetes, drawing on the Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset. Median imputation retained all 768 records, ROSE corrected a class imbalance of 0.537, and RFE selected ten predictors led by Glucose, BMI, and Age.

Random Forest delivered the best overall performance, with an F1 score of 0.5688, accuracy at 69.28%, and specificity of 0.7732. Logistic Regression produced the highest AUC of 0.7772, offering greater clinical flexibility through threshold adjustment. All four models hovered at a recall of approximately 0.58, the clearest finding of this study: the dataset had reached its predictive limit, and no algorithm could overcome it at this scale. The Random Forest Regressor's R^2 of 0.8790 for glucose prediction was the most encouraging result, pointing to a practical use case in settings where laboratory testing is not immediately accessible.

To use this kind of tool responsibly, it would need to be retrained on a wide range of patient groups, follow GDPR compliant data practices, and be used as a decision support tool under clinical supervision. Within these limits, the pipeline that is developed offers a reliable and transparent starting point. Moving forward, addressing the gaps in data and demographic coverage we've identified could really help push it closer to practical, real world use.

Word count excluding references = 3,056 words

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